

Soil and crop management

Root distribution of rainfed rices in the Cerrado of Brazil

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Approximately 35% of Brazil's rice is rainfed in the states of Goias, Minas Gerais, and Mato Grosso. Much of that is on highly weathered, clayey soils that are friable when wet, are porous, and retain little water. Upland yields are often limited by drought. An interdisciplinary program at the National Rice and Bean Research Center seeks to determine the variability of rooting habit of upland rice grown in those soils, and to develop techniques to screen plant materials for deep, well-developed root systems. Forty upland and lowland cultivars were planted in two oxisols: 1) a dark-red oxisol that had previously received heavy corrective lime and phosphate

applications and had approximately 60% aluminum saturation below 30 cm, and 2) an oxisol that had received no heavy lime and phosphate applications and had very low aluminum saturation. Root samples were taken 100 days after planting. Differences in leaf area index and rooting density (see table) were probably due to higher phosphorus levels in the plow layer of the first oxisol, which probably stimulated greater rooting density below 30 cm despite higher aluminum saturation at those levels. Intervarietal variability in rooting behavior was extreme in both soils; it was greater than that in plant height or leaf area index. Rooting density was positively and significantly correlated with plant height, but linear correlation coefficients were too low (0.18 to 0.54) to be used for predictive purposes. In general, Brazilian upland varieties had greater root development below 30 cm than other varieties tested.

existing roots by iron oxides further reduces their nutrient absorption capacity.

Iron toxicity can be overcome to a considerable extent by:

1. growing rice cultivars that are resistant to iron toxicity;
2. draining the rice fields at critical growth stages (a method being developed by the Chinese Mission on a large scale in the country);
3. burning and incorporating rice straw, which consists of silica and calcium; and
4. applying urea, basic slag, and muriate of potash as sources of nitrogen, phosphorus, and potassium.

Extensive work on the mentioned methods is being done by the Agronomy Department of Rice Research Station, Rokupr, under the Food and Agriculture Organization/International Institute of Tropical Agriculture Rice Project.

Some plant characteristics at 100 days in 40 rice varieties on two oxisols, Brazil.

Site	Aluminum saturation in soil	Mean plant ht (cm)	Mean LAI ^a	Mean rooting density (cm root/cu cm soil) at	
				0-30 cm	30-60 cm
National Rice and Bean Research Center, Goiania, Goias	60% below 30 cm	78	1.9	2.3	0.6
Agricultural Research Center for the Cerrado, Planaltina, Federal District	Very low at all levels	77	2.6	3.4	1.6
Test of significance by analysis of variance		ns	***	***	***

^aLAI = leaf area index. ns = not significant; *** = significant at P=0.001.

Iron toxicity in Sierra Leone rice

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Iron toxicity is one of the serious problems reducing rice yields in flooded soils in Sierra Leone.

Bronzing usually occurs at maximum tillering. Roots are short, coarse,

reddish or dark brown, and have a few rootlets. Bronzing usually appears on older leaves. In severe cases the leaf edges turn dark brown and roll toward the midrib. In some cases, yellowing starts at the tips of the lower leaves, moving toward the leaf base. In severe cases the leaves are dark yellow to orange. The high iron levels inhibit the formation of new active roots, and the coating of

A test of several sowing methods in Nigeria

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Examination of different sowing techniques indicates that certain methods can contribute to reasonable rice yields with a minimum of land preparation.

At South Chad Irrigation Pilot Project, sited on heavy montmorillonitic clay in northeastern Nigeria, seed that was broadcast directly into wheat stubble yielded 4,910 kg/ha. Broadcasting into a seedbed and incorporating with a light harrow yielded 5,060 kg/ha; rotacasting yielded 4,320 kg/ha. Direct seeding into flooded paddy yielded only 2,000 kg/ha.

The South Chad Irrigation Pilot Project is investigating cropping systems and cultural techniques for small holdings and for large mechanized production units. Its main irrigation scheme is under development.